

STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING MARKETING CAPABILITIES IN INTERNATIONAL COMPETITION OF HANDWOVEN FABRIC PRODUCT ENTREPRENEURS IN THE INDUSTRIAL PROMOTION CENTER REGIONS

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Warayu treewatsuwan *

Ph.D. Student in Development Strategy
Udon Thani Rajabhat University, Thailand

Krittikar Sanposh

Associate Professor, Faculty of Development Strategy
Udon Thani Rajabhat University, Thailand

*Corresponding Author

Bussagorn Suksan

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Development Strategy
Udon Thani Rajabhat University, Thailand

ABSTRACT

The article objectives of this research were to: 1) study the international competitiveness of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4 and 2) create a strategy for developing the international competitiveness of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4. Mixed qualitative and quantitative research. Phase 1: To study the international competitiveness of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4, Uses research the target group was 12 experts and 400 people, research tools include semi-structured interviews and questionnaires, analyzing the content data and using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Phase 2 to create a strategy for developing used by organizing a workshop. Target groups include 15 experts and 30 experts, the content data and summarize, confirm the development strategy suitability and feasibility. The research tools were suitability and feasibility assessment forms. To analyze data using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Research results. 1.

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The study of the international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric entrepreneurs in the Industrial Zone 4 found that the overall average value is at a high level. When considering each aspect of the international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric entrepreneurs, rank 1: products, rank 2: physical characteristics, rank 3: price, rank 4: process, rank 5: distribution, rank 6: personnel, and rank 7: marketing promotion. 2. The strategies for developing the international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4, are as follows: Strategy 1: developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in marketing promotion, Strategy 2: developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in personnel, Strategy 3: developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in process, development strategies, and the results of the evaluation of the suitability and feasibility of the strategies are at the highest level overall.

Keywords: The Strategy, Capability, Hand-woven Fabric Products, Industry Promotion Center Region 4.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, one of the policies driving the country's economy has been to focus on developing and promoting small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to create strength and sustainable growth. The government has included development and promotion guidelines by setting policies and strategies in some parts of the National Economic and Social Development Plan and enacting the Small and Medium Enterprises Promotion Act B.E. 2000 and set a plan to promote SMEs, which can be said that SMEs are important to the development of the country as seen from the economic value calculated as GDP (Gross Domestic Product) of 39.60 percent from the SME group and the employment rate accounting for 80.30 percent of the total employment in the country and is also the main mechanism for the development of large industries in the form of groups of downstream or supporting industries distributed in all regions of the country. However, the past development and promotion did not achieve the set goals because SMEs still have more weaknesses than strengths and the important impact is the economic integration of various regions that has increased business competition from the past, especially the result of the integration into the ASEAN Economic Community after 2015, which is one factor that drives the government and related agencies to urgently push for development and promote the potential and competitiveness of SMEs because entering the ASEAN Economic Community brings opportunities to expand the market along with increased competition from ASEAN member countries. In the 21st century, business organizations must cope with the competition that the many complexities and challenges in many forms that come from globalization that have changed the landscape of global trade, investment, and production in a new way where human capital, technology, goods and services can move freely across borders. Therefore, preparing to cope with competition in the 21st century (Chananin Satchayaphan, 2020) One approach that the government has taken to solve the problem is to promote the production potential of communities to be more self-reliant, especially products from local wisdom that are based on knowledge, expertise, skills, and experiences that have been passed down from generation to generation, allowing for more commercial production, which will lead to creating careers and generating income for families, resulting in the

development of the local community economy to be strong and self-reliant, and then expanding to the provincial, regional, and national levels, leading to exports, which are the goals of sustainable self-reliance. From the said policy, there has been a revival of many local wisdoms, whether in the form of developing one-village-one-product products or products of various community enterprise groups, which have been able to generate income and pass on knowledge that was almost lost to return again. Local woven fabric is one product that has been promoted by the said policy, causing many woven fabric groups to be successful in reviving their communities to be strong, well-off, and self-reliant by making the most of the resources and wisdom available in the local area (Tinakorn Buachu, 2021).

Industrial Promotion Center Region 4, Udon Thani Province, Department of Industrial Promotion, Ministry of Industry is an agency with a mission to promote, support, and develop the industry of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), community enterprises, and start-up enterprises, responsible for the upper northeastern region 1, including 5 provinces: Udon Thani, Nong Bua Lamphu, Loei, Nong Khai, and Bueng Kan. The Industrial Promotion Center Region 4 can upgrade local woven fabric entrepreneurs, process products, generate income, create careers, reduce unemployment, which Udon Thani Province is a famous production and distribution source of khit silk products, which is a unique identity of Ban Nakha. It has also developed product designs to be modern and suitable for various usage occasions. (Community Development Office Nong Bua Lamphu Province, 2018)

From the study of the marketing development of local woven fabric products distributed in community shopping malls, it was found that a number of entrepreneurs have transformed local woven fabrics into souvenirs to increase the value of local woven fabrics. However, the variety of products is still limited. Therefore, a marketing strategy must be planned to meet the needs and requirements of tourists. From the information mentioned above, the researcher sees the importance of conducting research on the strategy for developing the marketing capabilities of entrepreneurs of hand-woven fabric products in international competition. The research results can be applied by academics, stakeholders, and community producer groups, as well as various occupational groups, to manage the group to be strong and promote entrepreneurs to have hand-woven fabric products that can compete internationally and create economic sustainability for producers, community groups, and the country.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY

1. To study the development of international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4.
2. To create a strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4.

III. DELIMITATION OF THIS STUDY

This research focuses on studying the marketing potential and determining the development strategy for hand-woven fabric product entrepreneurs in the Industrial Promotion Center Region 4. The study is divided into 2 phases as follows: Phase 1 to study the development of international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4, step 1: Qualitative research, target group 12 people, step 2: Quantitative research, target group 400 people, Phase 2: to create a strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4, step 1: Draft strategy, target group 15 people, step 2: Evaluation of strategy, target group 30 people, using appropriateness and feasibility assessment form, analyzing basic statistics.

IV. METHOD IN THIS STUDY

This research used a mixed research method. The research was divided into 2 phases as follows:

Phase 1 research studies the development of international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4, is a variety of research (Mix Method Research). There are 2 steps as follows:

Step 1 study the development of international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4 conducting qualitative research. The target group is experts and stakeholders, including the directors of woven fabric promotion groups from the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4, the Provincial Commerce Office, the Provincial Community Development Office, educational institutions, totaling 6 people, and woven fabric entrepreneurs who are successful in selling woven fabric products, designers, community enterprises, or entrepreneurs who process and sell hand-woven fabric products, totaling 12 people. By selecting a specific type The research instrument used was a semi-structured interview. The data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using content analysis and overall summary,

Step 2 study the development of international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4 conducting quantitative research. The sample group used in this research was because the sample group did not know the exact population size. Therefore, the calculation method was used using Cochran's (1977) formula at a 95% confidence level. Therefore, the minimum sample size was 400 people. The research instrument was a questionnaire, which was a rating scale questionnaire . 5 levels according to Likert 's method (Likert's Method) (Bunchom Srisat, 2013 : 121-122). The quality of the questionnaire instrument was checked by five experts. The consistency index of each item of the questionnaire was not less than 0.70 and the reliability of the entire questionnaire was equal to 0.98 (Suchart Prasitratsin , 2003). Data were analyzed using statistics: frequency, percentage , mean, and standard deviation. This research study has been reviewed and approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee, Udon Thani Rajabhat University, project approval number 0622.7/ 278. On July 8,2024. Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage, mean, and standard deviation in the discussion of results; to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisat, 2010). The researcher distributed questionnaires, collected the data, and verified the completeness of the data in the questionnaire manually along with the questionnaire to interpret the results is the code according to the manual by entering the prepared code, saving, and processing. The data analysis obtained from closed-ended questionnaires and used as statistics mean analysis.

Phase 2: to create a strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4. The research is divided into 2 steps as follows:

Step 1: Determine the draft strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4, using the SWOT technique. Target group: 15 experts, including handwoven fabric experts from the Director of the Woven Fabric Promotion Group from the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4, the Provincial Commerce Office, the Provincial Community Development Office, educational institutions, 5 people; designers, academics in handwoven fabric fashion from educational institutions, 5 freelancers, and entrepreneurs who process and distribute handwoven fabric products at an international level, 5 people. By selecting a specific type Analyzed using content analysis and summarized in general.

Step 2: Evaluate the strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4, conducting quantitative research. Target group There are 30 experts with knowledge and experience, including hand-woven fabric experts from the Director of the Group that Promotes Hand-woven Fabrics from the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4, Provincial Commerce, Provincial Community Development, educational institutions, 5 people, designers, academics in hand-woven fabric fashion. From educational institutions, 5 freelancers and 20 entrepreneurs who process and distribute handwoven fabric products at an international level . By selecting a specific type Research tools, It is an assessment of the appropriateness and feasibility of the strategy for developing the international competitiveness of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4, by setting the scoring criteria as a rating scale using the Liker Method (Yutt Kaewwan , 2002), choosing a specific method (Purposive Sampling). Research instruments – The researcher used an assessment form to assess the suitability, feasibility of the strategy as a scale to perform scoring according to the criteria that determined the scores of the 5 weight ranges.

The researcher collected the data by calling the appointment in advance than taking the assessment together with a request for cooperation; and the researcher traveled to collect data by himself. Data analysis by content analysis and synthesis content then a descriptive overview was summarized and data analysis the researcher analyzed the data by using a ready-made program which analyzed frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The results were interpreted according to the following analytical criteria (Boonchom Srisat, 2010). The researcher has set the criteria that for the assessment to pass, the assessment must have a means of no less than 3.51 to be considered that the assessment is passed criteria.

V. CONCLUSION

From the research on create a strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4. The results of the research were summarized as follows:

Phase 1 The results of interviews in the study are the development of international competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4. Found that: 1) Lack of knowledge and skills in international public relations. Lack of budget for public relations activities. 2) Limitations in language and culture. Communicating with foreign customers requires different languages and understanding of cultures. 3) Lack of cooperation and networks with organizations abroad. 4) Competing with famous products and world-class brands. 5) Lack of understanding of target markets and customer groups. The Results were found that out of 400 respondents. Ranking 1 The product Rank 2 Physical Evidence is at a high 3rd place Price, No. 4 Process. No. 5 Distribution, No. 6 Personnel, No. 7 Marketing Promotion, It is at a high level respectively. As shown in Table 1

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Table 1. Level of international competitive marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4.

Marketing capabilities	Competency level			Ranking
	$\bar{x}$	S.D	Interpretation	
1. Product	4.38	0.83	a lot	1
2. Price	4.32	0.85	a lot	3
3. Distribution	4.31	0.83	a lot	4
4. Promotion	4.26	0.86	a lot	7
5. Personnel	4.29	0.83	a lot	6
6. Process	4.30	0.84	a lot	5
7. Physical Evidence	4.34	0.81	a lot	2
Total	4.31	0.84	a lot	

From the table, it was found that the mean and standard deviation of the level of international competitive marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4. It is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.31$, S.D = 0.84) When considering each aspect, ranking 1 The product is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.38$, S.D = 0.83), Rank 2 Physical Evidence is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.34$, SD = 0.81) 3rd place Price, It is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.32$, S.D = 0.85), No. 4 Process, It is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.30$, SD = 0.84), No. 5 Distribution ,It is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.31$, S.D = 0.83) No. 6 Personnel, It is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.30$, S.D = 0.84), No. 7 Marketing Promotion, It is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.26$, S.D = 0.86) respectively.

Phase 2 The strategy for developing the international competitive marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4 consists of:

1. The results of the study on the international competitiveness of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the Industrial Zone 4 found that: The problem of international competitiveness of textile product entrepreneurs Consisting of 1) Product 2) Physical Evidence 3) Price 4) Process 5) Place Strategy 6) Personal and 7) Promotion , which is consistent with the research of Thanawat Chatwiriyanon , Siravith Kunrojanapat and Sudawan Somjai, Researcher : Developing the Competitiveness of Thai Garment Entrepreneurs in a Sustainable Way. The research results found that marketing promotion has the most sustainable impact on the competitiveness of Thai garment entrepreneurs. The results of this research will enable Thai garment entrepreneurs to develop their competitiveness by focusing on the important aspect of marketing promotion (Thanawat Chatwiriyanon , Siravith Kunrojanapat and Sudawan Somjai , 2020) is also consistent with the research of Phet Thuksun , Nattharitha Mongkhonkiri. and Methinee Imeop, the study of the impact of marketing capabilities and business networks on the export success of Thai entrepreneurs to support entry into the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC). The research results found that the capabilities of product prices and marketing promotion of entrepreneurs who organized activities in this format Various things in foreign countries, including sales promotion, will stimulate product exports, resulting in increased efficiency of product exports (Phet Thuksun , Nathrida Mongkhonkiri) and Methinee Imeop , 2016)

2. The results of the evaluation of the draft strategy for developing the marketing capability in the international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4 found that the results of the evaluation of the strategy for developing the competitiveness of the handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4 Suitability is at the highest level, The feasibility of the strategy is at a high level is averaged above the 3.51 threshold. Strategic assessment of the development can be put into practice.

Table 2 Results of the evaluation of the strategy for developing the international competitive marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4.

strategy	Suitability level			Level of possibility		
	$\bar{x}$	S.D	Interpretation	$\bar{x}$	S.D	Interpretation
Strategy 1 Developing entrepreneurial capabilities in the field of promotion	4.48	0.62	a lot	4.28	0.64	a lot
Strategy 2: Development of entrepreneurial capabilities in terms of personal (personal)	4.74	0.53	Most	4.64	0.53	Most
Strategy 3: Development of entrepreneurial capabilities in process	4.53	0.70	Most	4.43	0.71	a lot
Total	4.58	0.61	Most	4.45	0.63	a lot

From the table, it was found that the results of the evaluation of the strategy for developing the competitiveness of the handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4 Suitability is at the highest level ($\bar{x}$ = 4.58 , S.D= 0.61) The feasibility of the strategy is at a high level. ($\bar{x}$ = 4.45 , S.D= 0.63)

VI. DISCUSSION

The researcher brought the findings for discussion. Details are as follows:

1.The results of the study on the international competitiveness of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the Industrial Zone 4 found that: The problem of international competitiveness of textile product entrepreneurs Consisting of 1) Product 2) Physical Evidence 3) Price 4) Process 5) Place Strategy 6) Personal and 7) Promotion , which is consistent with the research of Thanawat Chatwiriyanon , Siravith Kunrojanapat and Sudawan Somjai, Researcher : Developing the Competitiveness of Thai Garment Entrepreneurs in a Sustainable Way. The research results found that marketing promotion has the most sustainable impact on the competitiveness of Thai garment entrepreneurs. The results of this research will enable Thai garment entrepreneurs to develop their competitiveness by focusing on the important aspect of marketing promotion (Thanawat Chatwiriyanon , Siravith Kunrojanapat and Sudawan Somjai , 2020) is also consistent with the research of Phet Thuksun , Nattharitha Mongkhonkiri. and Methinee Imeop, the study of the impact of marketing capabilities and business networks on the export success of Thai entrepreneurs to support entry into the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC). The research results found that the capabilities of product prices and marketing promotion of entrepreneurs who organized activities in this format Various things in foreign countries, including sales promotion, will stimulate product exports, resulting in increased efficiency of product exports (Phet Thuksun , Nathrida Mongkhonkiri) and Methinee Imeop , 2016)

2. Results of the development strategy for developing the competitive marketing capabilities of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4 Consisting of strategic development issues 3 strategic namely

Strategy1: Developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in marketing promotion Organize activities, seminars on strategies for brand building and customer retention, effective sales promotion activities, and seminars on communication channels for product public relations. This is consistent with the research of Satayu Romyen on innovation capabilities and marketing capabilities that affect the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in the province. The research results found that marketing capabilities in communication and marketing capabilities in product development affect the performance of the business (Satayu Romyen, 2018).

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Strategy2: Development of entrepreneurs' capabilities in terms of personnel Activities: Training in developing customer service capabilities, and training in handling customer complaints. Training on customer and employee satisfaction measurement and regular employee training on products and services, product publicity Consistent with the research of Kanokphan Phatthaprinsiri on increasing the competitiveness of businesses by improving the quality of the Ministry's services. Commerce The research results found that the satisfaction of service recipients has an influence and affects the increase in the competitiveness of the business (Kanokphan Phatthaprinsiri, 2018). It is also consistent with the research of Winyaporn Pramanachoti on the relationship of modern marketing strategy factors that affect the creation of competitive advantages of local businesses to Chinese business ownership. The research results found that the positive factors that affect the creation of competitive advantages for local businesses include customer satisfaction (Winyaporn Pramanachoti, 2021).

Strategy3: Development of entrepreneurial capabilities in the process area Activities include training in sales or service processes to be transparent and easy to understand, seminars on responding to problems and customer needs, field trips and monitoring and evaluation of hand-woven fabric product processes , and training in service or production processes to be efficient, in line with research by Wasuthida Nakkesom and Prasopchai Pasunon on factors affecting the creation of competitive advantages for service business operators. In Bangkok area The research results found that the level of creating competitive advantage of service business operators in Bangkok with the highest average value was in the aspect of responding to problems and customer needs quickly (Wasutida Nakkesom and Prasopchai Pasunon , 2018).

The researcher has applied the textual format to create a strategic model for developing the marketing capability in the international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4. As follows:

Figure 1 Model of the strategy for developing the competitiveness of the international marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the current study, the author recommends the following measures as presented below:

1. Recommendation for applying the research results

Summary and recommendations from the research on the strategy for developing the international competitive marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, Region 4, found that the problem of the international competitive marketing capability of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs Consisting of 7 aspects: 1) Product 2) Physical Evidence 3) Price 4) Process 5) Distribution 6) Personal and 7) Promotion and strategy for developing marketing capability in international competition of handwoven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of Industrial Promotion Center Region 4 . Including Strategy 1: Developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in the area of marketing promotion, Strategy 2: Developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in the area of personnel, Strategy 3: Developing entrepreneurs' capabilities in the area of processes.

2. Recommendations for further research and development

From the results of this research, the following are suggestions:

The researchers have the following suggestions: 1) Suggestions for applying the research results The results of this research can be presented to the Industry Promotion Center, Region 4. Organize sales promotion activities, practice using online or offline advertising, train in developing customer service capabilities, field trip activities, and follow-up and evaluation of hand-woven fabric product processes. 2) Recommendations for future research by studying the strategy for developing the marketing capabilities in the international competition of hand-woven fabric product entrepreneurs in the service area of the Industrial Promotion Center, and other regions.

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